

Does Anyone Ever Notice?

Israt Jahan

English Language & Literature

University of Creative Technology Chittagong, Bangladesh

Does anyone ever notice
When stars fall in the dead of night?
Does anyone care
That the moon has lost some of its light?

Is the mountain stream still pure—
Or the rain falling from the sky?
A colored letter in a white envelope,
Red ink where black should lie.

No longer lost in thrillers now,
My mind is tangled in rhyme;
The teacup's cracked, the handle gone—
Dust gathers with time.

The old roadside tea stall waits,
But I haven't been there in years;
No rising steam in my favorite cup,
Just absence and silent tears.

My feet, once free,
Now follow paths unknown;
Daily duties drown the soul,
Like a heron in monochrome.

A slice of sun at noon
Mocks this slow decay,
Familiar times feel strange—
As sickness finds its way.

Why does time sometimes freeze?
Why can't it just move on?
Even the shy water lilies bloom
In kohl-lined ponds at dawn.

Bees bring no honey now,
But garlands from the field;
The forest trees stand silently,
To weary travelers, they yield.

The boats don't know who they'll carry
Or on which river they'll glide;
In the fair of longing, voices rise—
Youth sings, with no one by its side.

Still, the earth wears no smile,
Just as pale as a century ago—
Silent, slow, and hollow.